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GLOBAL WARMING AND SOLUTIONS FROM THE PALM OIL INDUSTRY

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RESUME

The palm oil industry has great potential to be part of the solutions to the global warming problem through five significant contributions. First, oil palm plantations act as carbon sinks that can reabsorb carbon emissions from the Earth's atmosphere. Second, oil palm plantations contribute to afforestation by converting lands with lower carbon stocks into oil palm plantations with higher carbon stocks. Third, providing renewable energy which has relatively lower carbon emissions as a substitute for non-renewable and high carbon emission fossil energy. Fourth, supplying food with relatively low emissions to replace more emission-intensive vegetable oils. And fifth, improving technology and management along the downstream industrial supply chain to reduce emissions in order to increase the Net Carbon Sink along the entire upstream-downstream supply chain of palm oil.

INTRODUCTION

Global warming is the most prominent and alarming issue of this century. The extensive and systemic impacts of global warming have captured the attention of the global community to continue discussing both the causes and solutions.

Naturally, the Earth's atmosphere is filled with Greenhouse Gasses (GHGs) with carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane (CH₄), and nitrogen (N₂) as the main components, all at certain natural concentrations. The function of these greenhouse gases is to form a natural greenhouse effect mechanism so that solar heat is trapped in the Earth's atmosphere at a level sufficient to protect and maintain a comfortable Earth's atmospheric temperature for life.

The increase in the intensity of the greenhouse effect in the Earth's atmosphere occurs when the concentration of GHG emissions in the Earth's atmosphere exceeds its natural concentration, causing more and more solar heat to be trapped in the Earth's atmosphere. As a result, the Earth's air is getting hotter (global warming), leading to global climate change.

Thus, in theory, there is a combination of two things that the entire global community must undertake to address global warming. First, finding ways to reduce the already high concentration of GHG emissions in the Earth's atmosphere. Second, determining the steps that can be taken to prevent the increase of GHG emissions (additional new GHGs) into the Earth's atmosphere. All countries, sectors, industries, companies, households and individuals on Earth need to take part in preventing and/or reducing GHG concentrations in the Earth's atmosphere.

This article will discuss the causes of global warming, namely the contributors to Earth's GHG emissions. Additionally, it will discuss the solutions that can be contributed by the palm oil industry in the collaborative effort to overcome global warming.

CONTRIBUTORS TO GLOBAL WARMING

The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) in 2018 revealed that the concentration of GHG emissions in the Earth's atmosphere has increased from the pre-industrial period (1800s) to the present day (PASPI, 2023^a). The concentration of CO₂ in the Earth's atmosphere has risen from 280 ppmv (parts per million volume) in the 1800s to 353 ppmv in 1990, and continued to increase to 379 ppmv in 2005. Subsequently, it rose to 396 ppmv in 2013, 399 ppmv in 2015, and further increased to 407 ppmv in 2018 (IEA, 2013, 2016, 2019). The United States National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) also revealed that the CO₂ concentration level in the Earth's atmosphere in May 2022 had increased to 417.6 ppmv.

The causes of the increase in GHG emissions come from human activities on Earth and the emergence of man-made gases such as the Chlorofluorocarbon (CFC) and halogen (human enhanced greenhouse effect) groups. Various empirical studies (IEA, 2016; Olivier *et al.*, 2022) have revealed that the energy (fossil) sector is the main contributor to global GHG emissions. Out of approximately 58.8 Gt CO₂ eq of global GHG emissions, around 73 percent is contributed by emissions from fossil energy (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Contributors to Global GHG Emissions (Source: Oliver *et al.*, 2022)

Therefore, it is quite clear that the main contributor to global GHGs which triggers global warming is the emissions from fossil energy consumption, especially from oil, coal and natural gas. These fossil energy emissions are the primary issue causing global warming, so the global community does not need to look for other sources or divert this issue to other sectors.

If the GHG emissions of this fossil energy can be significantly reduced, it will have a significant impact on decreasing global GHG emissions. There are indeed other sources of emissions, accounting for 28 percent, originating from other sectors such as agriculture (16 percent) and Land Use Change Land Use Change Forestry-LUCLUCF (12 percent), where these two sectors also need to contribute to reducing emissions. However, the emission reduction in the agriculture and LULUCF sectors will not have a big impact if the fossil energy emissions are not reduced significantly.

The IPCC (2023) has reiterated that the "new warning from the scientific community is to stop fossil fuels before it's too late". The warning means that the global community must be willing and strongly committed to reducing or even stopping the use of fossil energy before it is too late. Fossil energy producers should no longer fund multilateral NGOs to divert emissions and global warming issues or shift the blame to other sectors. This approach is not only futile but also creates new problems.

The global community also needs to switch from high-emission fossil energy use to lower-carbon emission energy sources. Food consumption must also shift from emission-intensive food to emission-efficient food.

At the same time, all efforts that can re-absorb Earth's atmospheric GHGs to reduce the concentration of these GHGs need to be a collective movement. Afforestation and reforestation by planting vegetation/plants that absorb carbon from the Earth's atmosphere should also be actively encouraged as a crucial part of the solutions in global warming mitigation.

PALM OIL AS PART OF THE SOLUTIONS

The global palm oil industry is one of the industries that has the potential to be part of the solutions for reducing global GHG emissions. Even oil palm plantations, often referred to as carbon plantations, also have an increasingly important role in reabsorbing carbon from the Earth's atmosphere.

There are five ways the global palm oil industry contributes to reducing and absorbing carbon emissions. First, oil palm plantations are carbon sinks. The production process in oil palm plantations is naturally a process of harvesting solar energy by absorbing CO₂ from the Earth's atmosphere so as to reduce the Earth's atmospheric CO₂ concentration.

Through the process of photosynthesis in oil palm trees, solar energy and CO₂ from the Earth's atmosphere are absorbed and transformed into palm oil, biomass, and some are stored in the form of soil organic carbon stocks. Based on his study, Henson (1999) revealed that oil palm plantations absorb CO₂ (through photosynthesis) from the Earth's atmosphere at a rate of 161 tons of CO₂ per hectare and reuse (respiration) about 96.5 tons of CO₂ per hectare; resulting in the net carbon sink of 64.5 tons of CO₂ per hectare for oil palm plants (Table 1).

Table 1. Oil Palm Plantations as Carbon Sinks

Indicator	Tropical Forest	Oil Palm Plantation
Gross assimilation (tons CO ₂ /ha/year)	163.5	161.0
Total respiration (tons CO ₂ /ha/year)	121.1	96.5
Net assimilation (tons CO ₂ /ha/year)	42.4	64.5
Oxygen production (tons O ₂ /ha/year)	7.09	18.70

Source: Henson (1999); PPKS (2004, 2005)

Oil palm plantations that have the potential to become Net Carbon Sinks (NCS) can reduce the concentration of carbon dioxide from the Earth's atmosphere. Carbon sinks in oil palm plantations can be even greater than in forest plantations. Palm oil and biomass produced from these oil palm plantations, further processed in the downstream palm oil industry, yield various food and health products (oleofood complex), oleochemical derivative products, and relatively low-carbon emission bioenergy/biofuels.

Second, oil palm plantations play a role in carbon absorption and carbon sequestration, this role can be seen as a form of afforestation, which is creating a "forest function" outside of forested areas. Through photosynthesis and bio sequestration processes, the carbon absorbed by oil palm plantations is converted into organic carbon stocks. Chan (2002) calculated the amount of biomass and carbon stocks (above ground biomass) resulting from carbon sequestration in oil palm plantations, ranging from 5.8 tons per hectare (in immature plants) to 45.3 tons per hectare (at the plant age of 20-24 years old) or an average of 30 tons of carbon per hectare.

Kusumawati *et al.* (2021) found that a one-year-old oil palm plantation contains a carbon stock of 43.5 tons per hectare and a 28-year-old oil palm plantation has a carbon stock of 74.7 tons per hectare. A study by Khasanah (2019) also revealed that the average carbon stock in above-ground biomass in Indonesia's oil palm plantations reaches 40 tons per hectare.

Various studies (Gunarso *et al.*, 2013^{a,b}; Suharto *et al.*, 2019) revealed that a significant portion of the land converted into oil palm plantations in Indonesia comes from land covers with lower carbon stocks compared to the carbon stocks of oil palm plantations (excluding peat oil palm plantations, which are still being debated). This means that land conversion (land use change) into

oil palm plantations is a carbon absorption (Net Carbon Sink) and not a carbon source. The net carbon absorption of LUC in oil palm plantations is also a result of biosequestration which reabsorbs carbon from the Earth's atmosphere.

Therefore, it is quite clear that through the process of photosynthesis in oil palm plantations, carbon from the Earth's atmosphere is reabsorbed, and through the process of biosequestration, the carbon is stored in the form of soil organic carbon stocks, which later becomes inorganic carbon in the soil.

Third, fossil energy substitution. The key to addressing global warming is to reduce the use of fossil energy, which is proven to be the largest contributor to global emissions (PASPI Monitor, 2021b; [PASPI, 2023^a](#)). On the other hand, energy is essential for life. Therefore, the solution lies in increasing the use of renewable energy which is relatively low in carbon emissions.

The palm oil industry becomes a part of the solutions because it provides low-emission renewable energy such as biofuels, namely biodiesel (PASPI Monitor, 2021^a, [PASPI, 2023^a](#)), palm biodiesel/palm oil-based green diesel (PASPI Monitor, 2022^a), and [palm oil-based avtur](#) and palm biomass-based bioenergy such as biocoal, biopellets, and biogas. Various studies have proven that biodiesel from palm oil can reduce emissions ([PASPI, 2023^a](#)). The European Commission Joint Research Center (2013) revealed that palm biodiesel produced from Palm Oil Mills implementing methane capture technology can achieve emission savings of up to 62 percent. The ability of palm biodiesel is also higher than other vegetable biodiesel such as sunflower biodiesel (58 percent), rapeseed biodiesel (45 percent), and soybean biodiesel (40 percent).

The study by Mathews and Ardyanto (2015) also supports the findings of the European Union, where the use of palm biodiesel as a substitute for fossil diesel can reduce GHG emissions by over 60 percent. The Euro Lex study (2009) also revealed that palm biodiesel is able to save emissions around 62 percent lower than the emissions produced from machines that use fossil energy.

Fourth, providing a substitute for the world's relatively high carbon emission vegetable oils. Internationally, there are four main vegetable oils in the world, namely palm oil, soybean oil, sunflower oil, and rapeseed oil. Of the four main vegetable oils, which one produces the lowest emissions?

Based on the studies by Beyer et al. (2020) and Beyer & Rademacher (2021), it was found that at the global ecosystem level, for every ton of vegetable oil produced, soybean oil has the highest emission intensity, followed by peanut oil, rapeseed oil, and sunflower oil. Meanwhile, the most emission-efficient source of vegetable oil is palm oil ([PASPI, 2023^a](#)). When compared to the carbon emissions generated from producing palm oil, the carbon emissions from soybean oil production are 425 percent higher, peanut oil emissions are 424 percent higher, rapeseed oil emissions are 242 percent higher, and sunflower oil emissions are 225 percent higher.

Fifth, reducing GHG emissions by improving the technology and management of the palm oil supply chain. In order to amplify the palm oil industry's contribution to global emission reduction and lowering the carbon concentration in the Earth's atmosphere, emission reduction along the upstream-downstream supply chain of palm oil can still be carried out. According to a study by Mathews and Ardiyanto (2015), during the production process from oil palm plantations to CPO Mills, the largest contributor to emissions is POME (62 percent), followed by fertilizers (31.5 percent) and fossil energy (5.1 percent). Meanwhile, in the downstream industry, the biggest contributor is energy for esterification and refining as well as transportation.

Emissions from POME can be reduced by approximately 97 percent through methane capture technology. Currently, only a portion of the oil palm plantations have adopted methane capture technology, so it needs to be further expanded in the future. Various studies (Seng *et al.*, 2021; Vincenza, 2021) have demonstrated that a combination of technological and management improvements in oil palm plantations can lead to significant emission reduction, even approaching nearly zero emissions.

With these technological and management improvements, emissions in the CPO production process will continue to decrease significantly (PASPI Monitor, 2022^b; [PASPI, 2023^a](#)). So if it is combined with the Net Carbon Sink resulting from photosynthesis in oil palm plantations, it will produce an even greater Net Carbon Sink (PASPI, 2023^b). This potential will be further enhanced through emission saving from energy usage, namely the substitution of fossil energy and petrochemicals with palm biodiesel and palm biomass.

CONCLUSION

Global warming, which results in global climate change, is caused by the increase in GHG emissions from human activities on Earth, leading to their concentrations in the Earth's atmosphere exceeding their natural concentrations. The main contributor to global GHG emissions is emissions from fossil energy. Overcoming global warming can be done through a combination of two ways, namely reducing GHG emissions to prevent an increase in their concentrations in the Earth's atmosphere and reabsorbing carbon dioxide in the Earth's atmosphere to restore its concentration to its natural level.

The palm oil industry has the potential to be part of the solutions to the global warming problem through five significant contributions. **First**, oil palm plantations act as carbon sinks that can reabsorb carbon emissions from the Earth's atmosphere. **Second**, oil palm plantations contribute to afforestation, namely converting lands with lower carbon stocks into oil palm plantations with higher carbon stocks. **Third**, providing renewable energy which has relatively lower carbon emissions as a substitute for non-renewable and high carbon emission fossil energy. **Fourth**, providing food with relatively low emissions to replace more emission-intensive vegetable oils. And **fifth**, improving technology and management along the downstream industrial supply chain to reduce emissions in order to increase the Net Carbon Sink along the upstream-downstream supply chain of palm oil.

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